

Studies on Copper(II) Ternary Complexes with Tartrate and 2-Amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-Substituted Derivatives

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Manuscript received 12 July 1985, revised 8 September 1986, accepted 30 October 1986

A series of copper(II) ternary complexes of the type $M[CuT(OH)L]$, where $M=Na^+$, K^+ ; T =tartrate ion; and L =2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (ATD), 2-amino-5-(phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (APTD), 2-amino-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (ACPTD) and 2-amino-5-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (AMPTD) have been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data. The coordinations of both the carboxylate groups, one of the secondary alcoholic group of tartrate ligand and amino group of another ligand 'L' have been indicated from infrared spectra, while magnetic and electronic spectral data indicate these complexes to be high-spin pentacoordinated.

PATEL *et al.*¹ have reported a very sparingly soluble copper(II) tartrate, $Cu(C_4H_4O_6)$ which gives a deep blue solution with NaOH or KOH and copper(II) hydroxide is not precipitated even with large excess of base. A deep blue sodium compound $Na[CuT(OH)]$ and similar potassium compound $K[CuT(OH)]$ are obtained by treating a saturated solution of copper(II) tartrate in the corresponding base with ethanol and these are known to form 1 : 1 addition compounds with uni/bidentate nitrogen donors^{2,3}. In recent years, 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-substituted derivatives have received much attention as potential bactericides, fungicides, insecticides and herbicides. There has been considerable interest in the study of their metal complexes with transitional metal ions and as a part of our continuing investigation on syntheses and structural elucidation of copper(II) complexes with tartrate and uni/bidentate ligands, we report in this communication a few copper(II) complexes with tartrate and ligands containing nitrogen and sulphur donors such as 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-substituted derivatives.

Experimental

The starting materials $M[CuT(OH)]$, where $M=Na^+$, K^+ , and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-substituted derivatives were prepared following the procedure reported earlier^{1,4}.

Preparation of complexes: To an aqueous blue solution of $M[CuT(OH)]$, ethanolic solution of appropriate ligand (L) was added in 1 : 1 molar proportion and the mixture was refluxed for about 1 h or till a green solution was obtained. It was cooled in a refrigerator when the crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered and the residue washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in

vacuum over fused calcium chloride. The compounds were analysed⁵ for their Cu, S and N.

All the compounds are highly soluble in water giving green solution, but insoluble in common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol and acetone *etc.* The molar conductance values of their 0.001 *M* aqueous solutions indicate them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes. The analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were determined at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the range 4 000–400 cm^{-1} using a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra (liquid paraffin) were recorded on a Spekol-ZV (Carl-Zeiss) spectrophotometer in the range 350–850 nm. The conductance measurements were carried out by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using 1×10^{-3} *M* aqueous solution of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1).

The general features of the infrared spectra are rather complex. Only the potential features which are important for the elucidation of structure have been discussed and comparison has been made with previously reported compounds. The ir spectrum of 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole exhibits two bands at $\sim 3\,350$ and $\sim 3\,100$ cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{as} N—H and ν_s N—H respectively⁶, whereas its 5-substituted derivatives show a strong and broad band at $3\,300$ – $3\,000$ cm^{-1} which may be due to overlapping of N—H stretching and C—H stretching vibration

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	Cu	N	S		
Na[CuT(OH)ATD]	17.98 (18.02)	11.78 (11.91)	9.06 (9.08)	1.82	120.5
K[CuT(OH)ATD]	16.86 (17.24)	11.24 (11.40)	8.62 (8.68)	1.84	128.2
Na[CuT(OH)APTD]	14.72 (14.82)	9.78 (9.80)	7.42 (7.48)	1.88	115.6
K[CuT(OH)APTD]	14.08 (14.29)	9.42 (9.45)	7.18 (7.20)	1.90	123.1
Na[CuT(OH)ACPTD]	13.24 (13.72)	9.02 (9.07)	6.82 (6.91)	1.92	105.4
K[CuT(OH)ACPTD]	12.98 (13.26)	8.62 (8.78)	6.56 (6.68)	1.84	117.5
Na[CuT(OH)AMPTD]	13.64 (13.85)	9.02 (9.15)	6.86 (6.98)	1.87	111.2
K[CuT(OH)AMPTD]	(13.39)	(8.85)	(6.74)	1.88	118.2

of phenyl group⁷. The other prominent bands observed for 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-substituted derivatives at ~ 1650 , ~ 1635 , ~ 1120 , ~ 910 , ~ 760 and 650 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$, cyclic $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\rho_r(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, $\rho_w(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$, respectively^{7,8}. In the present complexes, a strong and broad band is observed at $\sim 3400-3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This may be due to overlapping of O—H stretching vibration of secondary alcoholic group of tartrate and N—H stretching vibration of 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its 5-substituted derivatives. The ν_{OH} of water molecules may also fall in this region. However, all these complexes do not show any weight loss when heated even to 200° indicating the absence of either lattice or coordinated water molecules.

In the ir spectra of sodium potassium tartrate, a strong and medium bands are observed at ~ 1615 and $\sim 1460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. These are probably due to symmetric and antisymmetric vibration of carboxylate groups. In tartaric acid, sharp bands at 1750 and 1097 cm^{-1} have been assigned to carboxylic acid group and C—O stretching of secondary alcoholic group⁹. In the present complexes, a strong and broad band is observed at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ but no band is revealed at 1460 and 1750 cm^{-1} . This indicates the probable coordination of both the carboxylate group. The broad band may be due to overlapping of deformation vibration of NH_2 group with stretching vibration of tartrate shifted to this region on coordination. In lactate ion, the secondary alcoholic group has in-place O—H bending absorption at 1275 cm^{-1} which shifted to 1390 cm^{-1} on chelation with zinc¹⁰. In all these complexes, strong and medium bands are observed at ~ 1350 and $\sim 1240 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, which suggest that one of the secondary alcoholic groups is coordinated and the other is free. This is further confirmed by the appearance of split bands in the region $1100-1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ instead of single band as observed for tartaric acid or sodium potassium tartrate due to C—O stretching vibration of secondary alcoholic group. It is interesting to note that

instead of two split bands as observed in $\text{M}[\text{CuT}(\text{OH})]$ in this region, a group of three bands of medium intensity are observed in the present complexes. The middle band at $\sim 1060 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to rocking vibrational mode of NH_2 shifted to this region on coordination. The coordination of NH_2 group is further confirmed by red-shift of the band due to $\rho_w(\text{NH}_2)$ from 760 to 700 cm^{-1} . The bands observed at 1635 , 910 and 650 cm^{-1} due to cyclic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}}$ of the free ligand (L) do not shift or split in the complexes which conclusively prove non-coordination of ring nitrogen and sulphur atoms to copper(II). In spite of availability of tertiary ring nitrogen atoms, the system prefers coordination in the exocyclic amino group probably due to steric factor. Further, the bands appearing at ~ 1280 and $\sim 690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligands having chloro substituent and methoxy substituent may be due to $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{C}_1}$ stretching vibrations, respectively¹¹. These bands remain unaffected in the spectra of the metal complexes suggesting non-coordinating behaviour of chloro and methoxy groups towards the metal ions. $\text{Na}[\text{CuT}(\text{OH})]$ shows weak band at $510-540 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is probably due to Cu—O bonds. Besides, the present complexes show weak bands in the region $\sim 400-430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to Cu—N stretching vibration¹².

All the previous discussions lead us to propose the pentacoordinated structure for copper(II) complexes. This is further supported by magnetic and electronic spectral data. The effective magnetic moments of the complexes measured at room temperature are in the range $1.8-1.9 \text{ B.M.}$, suggesting them to be paramagnetic with an unpaired electron as expected for copper(II). The electronic spectra of all these complexes in solid state and in aqueous solution are almost identical. This indicates non-participation of water molecule in the coordination.

All the complexes exhibit two ligand field bands at ~ 10400 and $\sim 13700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in close agreement

with previously reported pentacoordinated copper(II) complexes under D_{3h} symmetry and may assigned due to ${}^2A'_1 \rightarrow {}^2E'$ and ${}^2A'_1 \rightarrow {}^2A''$ transition, respectively^{13,14}. The CT band is observed at $\sim 28\ 000\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes.

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